

Strain Rate Effect on In-plane Shear Strength of Unidirectional Polymeric Composites

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SUMMARY: This research aims at investigating the strain rate effect on the in-plane shear strength of unidirectional composites. Off-axis S2/8552 glass epoxy block specimens were employed to produce shear failure. Specimens were tested in compression at various strain rates. For strain rate less than 1/s, the experiments were conducted on an MTS machine. For higher strain rates, they were performed using a Hopkinson pressure bar. Experimental observations indicated that, for composite specimens with off-axis angles less than 10° , fiber microbuckling is the dominant failure mechanism. However, for the specimens with off-axis angles between 15° and 45° , in-plane shearing is the major failure mode. If the off-axis angle is greater than 45° , out of plane shear failure would take place. The shear strain rate was obtained from the uniaxial strain rate by relating the effective plastic strain rate to the plastic shear strain rate with the aid of a viscoplasticity model. Failure stresses for off-axis specimens obtained at different strain rates were then converted to a plot of shear strength versus shear strain rate. Experimental results showed that the shear strength of the composite is quite sensitive to strain rate; the shear strength increases when the strain rate increases. In contrast, the shear failure strain decreases as strain rate increases.

KEYWORDS: In-plane shear strength, Strain rate, Polymeric composites, Shear stress, Transverse normal stress

INTRODUCTION

Unidirectionally reinforced polymeric composites are generally weak in shear and transverse loading. Moreover, they are sensitive to loading rates. The quasi-static shear strength of composites has been investigated experimentally using the Iosipescu shear test [1] and a 10° off-axis tensile test [2]. In both experimental methods, in addition to shear stresses, transverse normal stresses are also present in the specimen, which may influence the value of the shear strength [3]. In order to obtain the pure shear strength, the effect of transverse normal stress must be accounted for in the data analysis. The rate effect on the interlaminar shear strength of carbon/epoxy composites was studied by Bouette et al [4] using simple lap shear specimen tested at a strain rate range of 10^{-3} - 10^3 /s. Although the specimen was designed with FEM analysis to reduce stress concentrations in the specimen, significant tensile peel stresses were still present. In [4], no influence of strain rate on the interlaminar shear strength of the composite was observed. Dong et al [5] proposed the design of a single lap specimen to estimate the interlaminar shear strength of composites under quasi-static and dynamic loadings. Both carbon/epoxy and carbon/PEEK composite specimens were tested. Experimental results showed that the interlaminar shear strength was not appreciably affected by strain rate. Ishiguro et al [6] investigated rate effect on unidirectional carbon/carbon composites using a double-notched lap shear specimen and found that the shear strength was influenced slightly by strain rate. Note that, in the above works, the rate sensitivity of interlaminar shear strength was of concern. In this study, the

strain rate effect on the in-plane shear strength of unidirectionally reinforced polymeric composites was investigated by testing off-axis block composite specimens at various strain rates. The failure mechanisms were examined and the failure load associated with the in-plane shear failure was determined. A viscoplasticity model was used to help deduce the pure in-plane shear strength and its sensitivity to shear strain rate.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

Low Strain Rate Test

With the presence of significant in-plane shear stresses, off-axis specimens subjected to a uniaxial loading are suitable for producing in-plane shear failure. To be consistent with the high strain rate testing using Split Hopkinson Pressure Bar, an off-axis block specimen with the dimensions of 1 x 0.6 x 0.6 cm was employed also for low strain rate testing. The block specimens were cut from a 75-ply unidirectional S2/8552 glass epoxy laminate using a diamond wheel. The fiber orientations considered included 15, 30, 45 and 60 degrees with respect to the loading direction. The specimens were lapped on a lapping machine with a 6 μm abrasive slurry to ensure smooth and flat loading surfaces. The contact surfaces of the specimens were lubricated to reduce friction. For low strain rates, uniaxial compression tests were performed on a servo-hydraulic MTS machine. A self-adjusting device as shown in Figure 1 was adopted to eliminate potential bending moments and also to ensure the specimen to be in full contact with the loading surfaces. The experiments were conducted under stroke control at three different strain rates, $10^{-4}/\text{s}$, $10^{-2}/\text{s}$ and $1/\text{s}$. The load history was recorded using LabView. The material constants for S2/8552 glass/epoxy composite are $E_1=50\text{GPa}$, $E_2=20\text{GPa}$, $G_{12}=6.9\text{GPa}$ and $\nu_{12}=0.3$.

Figure 1 Low strain rate compression test for brick specimens

High Strain Rate Test

High strain rate experiments were conducted using a Split Hopkinson Pressure Bar (SHPB), a simple and effective device for dynamic tests. Figure 2 shows the schematic of a conventional SHPB setup made of hardened steel bars with 12.7 mm (0.5 inch) in diameter. The striker bar had a length of about 101 mm (4 inch), and the incident bar and the transmission bar were 91 cm (36 inch) and 55 cm (22 inch) long, respectively. A pair of diametrically opposite gages (gage A) was mounted on the incident bar to measure both the incident and reflected signals. In the transmission bar, strain gages (gage B) were mounted about 16 cm (6.6 inch) from the specimen interface to measure the transmitted pulse. The strain gages on the bars were connected to Wheatstone circuits and then amplified using a Tektronix AM 502 amplifier. The signals were recorded using an oscilloscope at sampling rate 10MHz. Based on one dimensional wave propagation theory, the stress and strain histories of the tested specimen can be derived from the recorded signals. The off-axis block specimens employed

for SHPB tests were the same as those used in low strain rate tests to have the same properties. The strain rate range for the off-axis specimens in the SHPB tests is about 500/s. During the tests, the block specimen was sandwiched between the incident bar and the transmission bar. It is noted that shear-extension coupling takes place in off-axis specimens under axial loading. This behavior combined with bar-specimen interfacial friction could give rise to inhomogeneous deformation in the specimen, which deviates from the conventional Hopkinson bar assumption. In order to reduce the interfacial friction, all test specimens were lapped and lubricated as suggested by Ninan et al. [7]. A pulse shaper was used to produce a gently rising loading pulse which would help in extracting reliable stress-strain curves from SHPB tests [7]. This pulse shaping can be achieved using a piece of soft material inserted between the striker bar and the incident bar. A copper tab 1.7 mm thick was used as the pulse shaper in the present study.

Figure 2 Schematic of Split Hopkinson Pressure Bar

IN-PLANE SHEAR STRENGTH

Off-axis specimens tested at different loading rates were examined using an optical microscope to determine the failure mechanism. It was found that, for the 30° and 45° specimens, in-plane shearing is the major failure mode within the tested strain rates. Figure 3 depicts the in-plane shearing failure mechanism for a 30° off-axis specimen. For the 15° specimen, at strain rates above 1/s, the failure mechanism was still dominated by in-plane shearing; however, at lower strain rates, it was dominated by fiber microbuckling. For off-axis specimens with off-axis angles greater than 45°, out of plane shear failure would take place. In this study, the failure stress associated with in-plane shearing was of interest.

Figure 3. Shear failure mechanism for 30° specimen.

For off-axis specimens subjected to uniaxial loading, the in-plane shear stress σ_{12} is always accompanied by the transverse normal stress σ_{22} . Through the coordinate transformation law, the axial compressive failure stress can be decomposed into transverse normal stress and shear stress in the principal material directions. Thus, the state of failure can be expressed in terms of the combination of σ_{12} and σ_{22} as shown in Figure 4. The results of Figure 4 can be regarded as the in-plane shear strength of the composite in the presence of transverse normal stresses. It is important to

note that, in Figure 4, σ_{22} represents compressive stress. From Figure 4, it is noted that the transverse normal stress has little effect on the failure shear stress except for high strain rates and that the effect of transverse normal stress on the in-plane shear strength seems to be weakly proportional to the compressive stress σ_{22} . Thus, the pure in-plane shear strength can be obtained by extending the straight lines to the vertical axis corresponding to $\sigma_{22} = 0$. The pure shear strength and the corresponding axial strain rates obtained in this manner are listed in Table 1.

Table 1 Pure shear strength corresponding to different axial strain rates

Pure shear strength (MPa)	Axial strain rate (1/s)
99	0.0001
114	0.01
133	1
158	500

Figure 4 Effect of compressive transverse normal stress on shear strength

IN-PLANE SHEAR STRAIN RATE

In the off-axis test, the strain rate was measured in terms of the total strain in the loading direction. To characterize the strain rate effect on the shear strength, the rate of shear strain should be used. In view of the foregoing, the shear strain rate should be extracted from the uniaxial compression tests.

By subtracting the elastic component from the total strain rate $\dot{\epsilon}_x$, the plastic strain rate $\dot{\epsilon}_x^p$ is given by

$$\dot{\epsilon}_x^p = \dot{\epsilon}_x - \dot{\epsilon}^e = \dot{\epsilon}_x - \frac{\dot{\sigma}_x}{E_x} \quad (1)$$

The corresponding effective plastic strain rate $\bar{\dot{\epsilon}}^p$ is [8]

$$\bar{\dot{\epsilon}}^p = \frac{\dot{\epsilon}_x^p}{h(\theta)} = \sqrt{\frac{2}{3} \left[\left(\dot{\epsilon}_{22}^p \right)^2 + \frac{1}{2a_{66}} \left(\dot{\gamma}_{12}^p \right)^2 \right]} \quad (2)$$

where $h(\theta)$ is an off-axis parameter defined as

$$h(\theta) = \sqrt{\frac{3}{2}} \left[\sin^4 \theta + 2a_{66} \sin^2 \theta \cos^2 \theta \right]^{1/2} \quad (3)$$

It is noted that the effective plastic strain rate consists of two parts, i.e., the plastic normal strain rate

$\dot{\epsilon}_{22}^p$ and the plastic shear strain rate $\dot{\gamma}_{12}^p$. By employing a one-parameter plastic potential

$$f = \frac{1}{2} \left(\sigma_{22}^2 + 2a_{66} \sigma_{12}^2 \right) \quad (4)$$

together with the associated flow rule, the two strain rates can be expressed in terms of the normal stress and shear stress respectively as [8]

$$\dot{\epsilon}_{22}^p = \sigma_{22} \dot{\lambda} \quad (5)$$

$$\dot{\gamma}_{12}^p = 2a_{66} \sigma_{12} \dot{\lambda} \quad (6)$$

where $\dot{\lambda}$ is a proportionality factor and a_{66} is an orthotropy coefficient in the one parameter plastic potential. The value of a_{66} for the S2/8552 glass epoxy composite was found to be 6.0 [9]. Uniaxial off-axis loading is proportional loading, and, as a result, the relation between the plastic normal strain rate and the plastic shear strain rate is obtained as

$$\dot{\epsilon}_{22}^p = \frac{-\sin \theta}{2a_{66} \cos \theta} \dot{\gamma}_{12}^p \quad (7)$$

By substituting eqn (7) in eqn (2), the plastic shear strain rate can be obtained from the effective plastic strain rate as

$$\dot{\gamma}_{12}^p = \frac{\dot{\bar{\epsilon}}^p}{\sqrt{\frac{2}{3} \left[\frac{1}{2a_{66}} + \frac{\sin^2 \theta}{4a_{66}^2 \cos^2 \theta} \right]^{1/2}}} \quad (8)$$

By adding the elastic part of the shear strain, the total shear strain rate is calculated as

$$\dot{\gamma}_{12} = \dot{\gamma}_{12}^e + \dot{\gamma}_{12}^p = \frac{\dot{\sigma}_x \sin \theta \cos \theta}{G_{12}} + \dot{\gamma}_{12}^p \quad (9)$$

where G_{12} is the in-plane shear modulus. With eqn (8) and eqn (9), the shear strain rate can be obtained from the experimentally determined uniaxial stress and effective plastic strain histories. Figure 5 illustrates the effective plastic strain curves for 30° and 45° specimens corresponding to

strain rate 0.01/s. By taking the derivative of the final portion of the curve, the effective plastic strain rate at the instance of shearing failure was obtained. It is noted that there is some scatter in effective plastic strain rates obtained from different specimens, and, as a result, the estimated shear strain rates for the specimens with various fiber orientations are somewhat different. The shear strain rate presented in the next section was the averaged value of the individual shear strain rates associated with the same axial strain rate.

Figure 5 Effective plastic strain history for 30° and 45° specimens at axial strain rate 0.01/s

RESULTS

The pure shear strengths obtained from Table 1 for four different axial strain rates are plotted versus shear strain rate in Figure 6. It is seen that the shear strength of the composites is quite sensitive to strain rate and it increases as the strain rate increases. It is interesting to note that, on the semi-logarithmic plot, the dependence of shear strength on shear strain rate appears to be linear. By use of the viscoplasticity model [9], the failure shear strains corresponding to the failure shear stresses for different strain rates were determined. Figure 7 shows the plot of failure shear strain versus shear strain rate.

Figure 6 Shear failure stress versus shear strain rate.

Figure 7 Shear failure strain versus shear strain rate.

CONCLUSIONS

Off-axis block specimens of unidirectional S2/8552 glass epoxy were tested in compression to failure at various strain rates. Experimental results indicated that for 30° and 45° specimens, in-plane shearing was the major failure mode at strain rate up to 500/s. For the 15° specimen, at strain rate above 1/s, the failure mechanism was dominated by in-plane shearing; however, at lower strain rates, the failure mechanism became fiber microbuckling. The in-plane shear strength increases when strain rate increases. The presence of transverse normal stress does not seem to have much effect on the shear strength. On the other hand, the shear failure strain decreases when the strain rate increases.

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